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Teachers' Professional Development in the Process of Workers' Training for Worldskills Championships' Participation

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Abstract

The comparative-pedagogical study of the systems of professional-pedagogical education both in Russia and abroad can be considered very actual, while the processes of globalization and integration influence greatly upon the transformation of the existing educational paradigm. It manifests itself both in the estimation of essential characteristics of professional-pedagogical education, as well as in the attitude towards vocational education and training (VET): thus, it is becoming more attractive for students – future specialists of the labour market in accordance with the opportunity to participate in the international movement "Worldskills". Thus the problem of professional development of teachers, able to form a completely new type of a working person – creative, flexible to the changes in the globalizing world, responsible and active is of a particular importance at the present moment.

The demand for results of conducted research is determined by the ability to re-think and over-estimate critically the conceptual basis of the system of professional development of teachers, to define vectors of its development in accordance with major educational trends and tendencies, to enlarge pedagogical resource of teaching and learning in the system of higher pedagogical education.

Keywords: professional-pedagogical education; teachers' training, workers' education and training; Worldskills Championship; comparative analysis; adaptive-educational potential.

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Introduction

1.1 Modern tendencies in VET

Challenges to the system of professional development of the pedagogues are deeply interconnected with the processes of globalization and international educational integration, which are influencing significantly on the system of education in all countries in the world, including Russia. It should be pointed out not only about the most visible results of these processes (such as, unified educational area formation, prevalence of permanent changes on the condition of stability, shortening of geographical space, new types of inter-connection of global and local practice, virtualization of multiple life spheres, etc.), but we should speak about the changing of the entire *paradigm* of education, i.e. appearance of new trends, vectors, values and motivations. Meanwhile modernization of Russian vocational schools implies enhancing international activity and cooperation, which are, as professor T.Tregubova suggests, “multi-functional means of its strategic development” (Tregubova, 2016).

The increasing interest towards the comparative pedagogical research in the sphere of VET is determined by the search of constructive educational policies which would make social educational perspectives better in the conditions of integration and competitiveness on the labour market and service, stimulating innovative transformations in order to raise the level of efficiency and the quality of VET.

World- famous Russian researchers (Mukhametzyanova, 2010), (Shishov, 2016), (Tregubova, 2008) believe that Russian vocational school today has become the subject body of the relations in the global labour market, that caused transformations in its structure, search for innovative resources for financing, development of innovative technologies of teaching and learning as well as realization of social functions, such as: social control, social testing, thorough choice of the working youth (entering the independent professional working life), support and social protection of both student and pedagogue in VET. Changing of social functions of educational organization actualizes the problem of constructive preparation of the staff and its proper realization in the conditions of modern globalizing world. Although there can be observed some difficulties in the economic development of the modern Russian society that prevent from the realization of the social functions of modern vocational school, orientation on the international experience of organization of the following activity and preparation of the staff could be very useful for theoretical over-estimation of the conceptual basis of VET.

1.2 Actuality of implementation of international experience on VET

Social and pedagogical importance and perspective of studying international experience of professional preparation and professional growth of the pedagogues is obvious, while there are at least 3 factors proving it:

1. Enrichment of Russian pedagogical science and practice with the best results of the work of leading European countries and countries with developed market economy in the sphere of education has become an integral factor of its modernization and is considered to be the norm of scientific interaction as a revealed tendency of globalization of educational space.

2. In the modern paradigm “lifelong learning” (LLL), the implementation of which defines the general directions of development of unified international “zone of professional development” the professional growth of a pedagogue plays a key role: new goals and vectors of pedagogical education are being defined. It implies preparation of a new kind of teacher, possessing wide range of professional

competencies, able to accept and realize innovations in the professional sphere, “European” teacher, teacher with international orientation. All this influence on the level of consciousness of a pedagogue towards the necessity of European cooperation for the training and re-training of pedagogues able to fulfill the activity in accordance with the Bologna principles. The profession of a teacher is the hardest profession according to the degree of responsibility for the possibility to all the citizens of a democratic society to acquire competences and “learn the crafts” (Schmitt, 2006).

3. Knowledge of international experience of professional growth of pedagogues is important and valuable not for the purpose of mechanical borrowing of educational paradigms and adapting them for “local needs” (Tregubova, 2013), but for the determination adaptive-educational potential of the international experience, which can be considered as a vector and a resource for the perfection of the Russian system of professional development of pedagogues and for the over-estimation of pedagogical phenomena of inter-action and enrichment.

Methods of the research

The goal (aim of the study) is to make a comparative analysis of foreign and Russian system of professional development of teachers, pointing out the presence of deep inner interconnection of the international reforming tendencies within national educational traditions, global educational trends and Russian history-long educational peculiarities.

The objective of the study is to examine and typologize multi-faceted, diverse, unique experience of reforming of the teachers’ professional development system, while there can be observed convergence of the systems, the various forms of which are achieved due to the definite cultural-educational paradigm of each country.

The research examines modernization of Russian system of professional development of teachers for vocational and tertiary education as a key condition of activities, partnership and co-work of educational institutions all over the world in accordance with Worldskills Championship.

It is valuable that in the article, the adaptive-educational potential of international specialists’ training for the sphere of VET that may be implemented in Russian vocational schools, is presented, taking into consideration a unique way of development and improvement of Russian vocational specialists.

Theoretical value of the research lies in the determination of basic characteristics and major features of modern Russian system of teachers’ development in the comparison with foreign analogue systems, outlining the main vectors of professional-pedagogical education development within the process of international educational integration.

The practical part of the research can be seen in “Comparative table of the markers of existing system of final assessment of SVE- students and participants of Worldskills Championships”, which can be treated as innovative and can be implemented at Final Assessment in other professional and vocational establishments.

Methods of the research

A wide range of research methods were used in our research, such as: comparative analysis of international and Russian experience of VET (with pointing out the major problems and perspectives of its development); synthesis of modern approaches towards the phenomena “VET”, “Worldskills Championship”, “Training of pedagogues”, “Worldskills competences”/ “Future skills”, and “international experience”; multi-faceted analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature on the research problem.

Experimental basis of the research

Experimental bases of our research are the participants of the Championship “Worldskills Russia”, who are representatives of different Russian cities and promoting their professional competencies.

Stages of the research

1st stage: Stating experiment. A theoretical analysis of the following problem: transfer and adoption of international experience on preparation of the working staff for the qualitative work and Worldskills International Championship.

2- nd stage. Forming experiment. Comparison of existing assessment technologies on the professional activities of the working staff in Russia and abroad.

3-rd stage: Control experiment. Determination of the innovative adaptive –educational potential in the international experience suitable for the Russian educational environment.

Results

Comparative – pedagogical research, that is conducted in the Institute of Pedagogy, Psychology and Social Problems is designed not only for the determination and localization of new tendencies and educational phenomena, perspectives for the development of VET in the conditions of globalization and integration, but for defining the adaptive-educational potential of the international experience as a resource and vector for modernization of individual problems and aspects, for the formation and development of working professions in the conditions of Worldskills Championship. We have noticed that organizations of SVE are actively participating in the Worldskills movement. Their participation allows experts and tutors to improve significantly, to develop material – technical base, to update the methodology of evaluation of educational and professional achievements of the learners, be oriented on the best practices and standards. That would guarantee competitiveness on the labour market.

Stating experiment

There was done a deep theoretical analysis on the problem of research (implementation of international experience). Based on the opinion of foreign (Gurria, 2012), (Mckinney, 2007) and Russian (Alexeeva, 2016), (Butrim, 2017), (Krivonos, 2017) scientists we defined four levels of difficulties for transferring and adapting international experience:

First of all, there are problems of conceptual level connected with different approaches to the social value of VET. In the countries with developed market economy, there is a constructive mixture of social classes via means of VET, while in the European countries getting education is the only way to increase one’s social status.

The second level of difficulties – are those connected with the information barrier. Russian researchers, as a rule, do not possess the whole information about different aspects of solution of some educational or social problem. The information is fragmentary and is not objective.

The third level - adoption problems - these are technological barriers. They appear in accordance with the fact that new adequate ideas and recommendations on implementation of the elements of international experience in VET of the working staff and the technology of its implementation do not coincide with the existing Russian conditions. Changing of the separate, individual elements may lead to breaking – off the system in general.

The fourth level – these are psychological problems. To this group belong coping with old traditions, refusal to implement foreign experience in the educational sphere and v.v. too much assurance that foreign experience is better than Russian.

Forming experiment

We have conducted an analysis of the system of secondary vocational education (SVE) and participation in the international Championship Worldskills on the most actual and up-to-date positions. We have found out, that both systems have their advantages and disadvantages. We have made a table showing the innovative character of the International Championships, so that the practice of Final Assessment of SVE-leavers may be updated with the Championship principles and key positions. (Table 1).

Table 1

**Comparative table of markers (identifiers) of the existing system of final Assessment of SVE
–students and the participants of Worldskills Championships**

o.	Marker	Existing system of final assessment (SVE)	WorldSkills system
.	Responsibility for the functioning of the system	VET organization	Business and the community of professionals
.	Learning Material preparation responsibility	Pedagogical staff of the organization in the agreement with the head of organization	Experts on the definite competence in the agreement with the expert of the Championship
.	Role of the Chairman / expert	Independent of the Commission members on the level of qualification.	Independent from the Commission of the experts. Introduces 30% changes in the tasks of Championship. Final report is signed and is placed on the official web-site of the Championship.
.	Practical value of the performed work	The following part of work is performed in the organization according to the field standards.	The following part of work is designed specifically for the Worldskills Championship in accordance with its high-quality standards.
.	Work assessment	Based on the “Law of Education” on the 5 –grade system.	100 – grade system gives an opportunity for more exact diagnostics of the definite working abilities and skills.
.	Criteria of assessment	In the studying process all the practical works are supported by control and measure material with the criteria of assessment. The SVE- leavers have free access to it.	The participants of the Championship know just measures for the abilities and skills. Grading for each element is unknown.

Control experiment

We gathered, collected and systemized information of the comparative analysis of international experience implementation (based on Worldskills Championship) and we managed to found out adaptive and educational potential of the international experience on VET designed for enrichment the system of VET with the theory of professional preparation of Russian qualitative workers in the conditions of unified educational space:

1. Implementation of major conceptual ideas of synchronic changes in the development of the system of VET (multi-variety of standardization along with unification of European standards; globalization and regionalization; “organized diversification” with the creation of non-University sector of Vocational School with the shortage to 2-3 years of education and non-traditional educational Institutions; multi-subjective character of educational policy; openness and clarity; liquidation of brain-drain; development of the culture of patronship and donation for the purpose of professional development of the working staff).

2. Consideration of specific features of diversified preparation of the working staff in the EU – countries and countries with developed market economy (marketing orientation; acceleration of the processes of global integration; consulting on the basic part of its context; determination of existing lack of professional knowledge and skills; multi-level structure of the development of professional competence, accentuation on basic competences formation etc.).

3. Transformation of the context of professional development taking into account race, ethnic, gender variety; development of mobile variety system of studying disciplines of the vocational cycle, taking into account individual features and needs of each personality; increase of practice-oriented types of activities, influencing on the results of education and enhancing upbringing and educational functions; implementation of the integral approach towards the formation of the context of education, realized in multi-disciplinary and trans-disciplinary general and specified causes.

4. Implementation of innovative technologies in the process of qualified preparation of the working staff with the orientation on the development of the personality of the student while choosing and implementing: module-based organization of education and its various modifications, allowing to react in the most appropriate and flexible way on the personalities’ needs, in particular, and necessities of the society in general; mixture of individual and group technologies; intensification of contacts and diversification of the forms of interaction between teaching staff and learners; implementation of the technologies of the independent work and its scientific –methodological and organizational support.

Discussions

Decades-long experience of comparative research, determination of the possibilities of implementation of the separate elements of the International experience in the Russian vocational schools, spending various block-seminars and master-classes proved the possibility of implementation of the international experience for the professional growth of a pedagogue. Moreover, questionairing of the pedagogues of different ages and the pedagogical staff showed that the questions of teaching activities of the foreign partners are interesting and significant for the majority of pedagogues of the Russian vocational schools, while the desire to get acquainted with the possibilities of professional growth of a pedagogue abroad expressed 84% of respondents.

According to the scientific opinion of some of the researchers (Euroskills report, 2017), (Mukhametzyanova, 2006), (Petrochenko, 2017), (Tregubova, 2018), international educational cooperation is the process for establishment of equal and fruitful for both parties partnership within the subjects of education and consumers of the results of educational process: individual participants (students, University teachers, researchers, administrators), systems and educational institutions, state educational organizations and international organizations. Foreign colleagues have already come across most of the problems, that are Russian specialists facing in accordance with Copenhagen and Bologna processes: enhancing access towards education via means of distant education; solving the problems connected with non-substantial state financing; institutional autonomy; nationalization of the processes in the sphere of VET and etc.

Prof. Tregubova believes that “comparative studies of international experience possess a special value and cause a growing interest of the society while in the whole world, including our country, there are serious qualitative transformations in the essence of the characteristics, changing of paradigm, vision of the tasks and role of VET in the modern society, in particular, in the deeper inter-connection of the modernization of the system with national education traditions, global peculiarities, along with regional cultural and historical uniqueness and international educational integration”.(Tregubova, 2008).

So we should refuse old prejudice and stereotypes towards our foreign partners, evaluate their real success in the sphere of VET of the working staff and find out the unique way of Russian professional development. Foreign researchers of VET also pay attention to this (V.Deveor, B. Laggei, G.Weik and others) (Gurria, 2012) who ask not to copy their experience, but thoroughly over-estimate it so that general tendencies of the world be reflected in the national educational practice and the international theory and practice may be enriched by the modernization of VET.

In the process of studying specialized literature, participation in the international forums and conferences and as a result of authors' individual research it was stated that in the EU countries, countries with developed market economy, Canada and etc. all the educational institutions on the after-school level are treated as “separate actors” on the service market in the sphere of Education.

Quick tempo of changes (both in global and regional aspects) succeeded to the new “educational boom”, which implies global modernization and transformation of the system of VET. There are objective bases (Professional standards, 2007), (Frumina, 2008), (Spenser, 2005) for realization of the modernization of the system of professional development of a pedagogue in the form of 2 inter-connected processes: 1) modernization of the existing system; 2) formation of a new paradigm, conceptual approaches and conditions for its modernization on the bases of perspective evaluations taking into account constructive international experience in this sphere.

Thus, we can conclude with the following rule: for the successful adoption of international experience one must thoroughly choose and critically over-estimate the borrowed material, define the criteria for the choice (actuality, innovative character, optimality, high level of efficiency, implementation of innovations in the mass experience), which would allow to compare Russian and foreign preparation of the specialists of vocational school. If the process of borrowing doesn't result in a ready educational product, special conditions must be done for the constructive realization of the tasks with further transfer of the International experience.

Defined criteria are the determinants of successful implementation of the international, authentic experience of professional growth and development of a pedagogue and imply the appropriate choice for approaches and technologies of scientific-methodological support, taking into account specific features and

social-professional needs for the University teachers as well as the demands of the employees to the school-leavers and the needs of the global labour market.

However, there are a range of factors, preventing from successful implementation of the International experience of professional growth of a pedagogue. First of all, it is connected with the different interpretation in the definitions, logic apparatus, methodological bases and order of actions on the development of the mechanisms of the professional growth of a pedagogue, methodology of creation diversified programmes and educational products in the following process. The solution of the problem we can notice in the creation of theme vocabulary-glossary accepted at the Russian and international levels.

Conclusions and recommendations

To sum up, one of the most constructive forms of the development of international cooperation of Russian and foreign vocational schools is participation in the programmes “Worldskills International”, which allow unique possibilities for the experience exchange and comparison of the standards of the competencies on the working professions in the different sectors of global economy and suggests real assistance in the search of cost-efficient solutions for the development of International cooperation, oriented on the achievement of high standards in the vocational teaching and learning,

Analysis of specialized literature on the subject of the research showed that employees are interested in the Worldskills Championship: along with the prestigious status of the international Championship, it helps to engage high-qualified working staff in the company and create a strong personal branding of a worker as a specialist. So that cooperation with Worldskills helps to promote personal marketing programme, stimulating more successful development of the organization.

As it was stated above, the methodological bases of adaptive – educational potential and value of International experience of VET of the working staff in the conditions of Worldskills Championship were defined, so that the contribution is not limited by the addition of relevant data to the system of knowledge about this process, so that it performs the formation of a modern worldview and estimation of the learners.

Huge humanitarian potential and value is revealed in the studying of international experience of VET in the conditions of the Worldskills movement as a special invariant of international educational experience in the adaptive – educational potential for the harmonious integration of Russian vocational school in the unified educational space. The potential is actualized in the conditions of:

- 1) regularities and principles, approaches towards the models of management, context of education, technologies of preparation on the bases of comparative character and generalization are set up;
- 2) inter-relationship between global tendencies and regional specific features are defined;
- 3) unification of vectors towards flexibility and module-based character for the professional preparation of the learners is fixed via the formation of universal social-professional and key competences;
- 4) practice of successful adoption and transfer of models of the organization of VET in various social – professional and educational contexts is revealed for the supplying a completely new quality of VET.

Without no doubt, implementation of adaptive-educational potential, concluded in the international experience of the professional development of a pedagogue influences and determines the development of Russian theory and practice of the system of VET and defines the vector of its constructive development, enriching it with new and innovative content, that’s why this experience is

suitable for implementation in the Russian vocational school after its adoption and preparation of necessary conditions for its successful realization.

The value of international experience on the professional growth of a pedagogue can't be limited only by contribution to the system of knowledge about the functioning of foreign vocational school. The most valuable part of implementing international experience is that acquiring of the international experience by pedagogues, experts, researchers and possessing the scientific-comparative approach of transformation of the system of professional growth of a pedagogue turns him into a multi-cultural personality, globally-oriented, professionally – gifted, flexible, able to change in the process of re-training.

Conclusions on the results of the analysis of the international experience of professional growth of a pedagogue allowed to specify the directions of the development of the system of the quality assessment, among them there are: preparation and publication of Annual Manuals, reports about the development of the system of enhancing pedagogues' quality, inclusion of the innovative approaches to the monitoring of the system which is positioned as a resource for enhancing the level of quality aimed at professional growth support and implementation of criteria approach to the system of qualification training of a pedagogical staff with the list of self-assessment (achievement list). Knowledge and consideration of the foreign experience allows us to be sure that modernization of Russian VET goes along with monitoring, comparative assessment of the results education and socialization, there must be done a constant correspondence of the results of Russian educational practice to the international standards and norms. At the same time we must admit that experts of international organizations state 'which solutions could be achieved, they must be peculiar Russian – reflecting its history, values and traditions of Russian academic culture'. Moreover, "the solution of the problem must be truly "Russian" by its nature and correspond to its social, cultural and juridical traditions of Russian Federation" (Spenser,2008).

In the situation of diversification of VET and the global market of educational service, from the one hand, and globalized and integrative processes, from the other hand, there can be observed a definite convergence in the system of VET of the working staff from the position of goal –setting and mechanisms, forms of realization of which for the achievement of goals and tasks differ due to their traditions, cultural and educational paradigm of the country.

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